

IMPROVING PD-L1 EXPRESSION PREDICTION IN NON-SMALL CELL LUNG CANCER USING RADIOMIC ANALYSIS AND DEEP LEARNING MODELS ON WHOLE-BODY VS LUNG ^{18}F -FDG PET/CT DATA

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Abstract Lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer-related deaths world-wide. Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) account for 85% of lung cancer cases. Accurate assessment of Programmed Death-Ligand 1 (PD-L1) expression is essential for guiding immunotherapy decisions; however, conventional detection methods such as immunohistochemistry (IHC) are invasive and may not fully account for tumour heterogeneity. This study investigates the potential of deep learning-based models to predict PD-L1 expression using radiomic features extracted from full-body and lung-segmented ^{18}F -FDG PET/CT scans. Radiomic features were extracted from 134,590 full-body and 43,142 lung slices obtained from 308 NSCLC patients. Fully Connected Neural Networks (FCNNs) were trained and optimized with different network depths, activation functions, dropout rates, and optimizers. Models trained on whole-body data consistently outperformed those using lung data, emphasizing the importance of systemic metabolic information. At the feature level, the best FCNN model achieved 99% accuracy and an ROC-AUC of 0.997, while at the patient level, it achieved 98% accuracy and an ROC-AUC of 0.995. The findings highlight the superiority of deep learning-based full-body radiomic analysis over localized imaging in predicting PD-L1 expression. This approach demonstrates the potential of FCNNs as a non-invasive diagnostic tool, providing an advanced framework for precision oncology and NSCLC immunotherapy decision-making.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide, with 1.8 million people dying of lung cancer every year [1], highlighting the urgent need for more effective diagnostic and therapeutic strategies. In the United Kingdom, lung cancer is the third most prevalent cancer [2]. About 85% of lung cancer is classified as non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). Over the past decade, the treatment landscape for NSCLC has evolved significantly and in addition to traditional modalities such as surgery, radiotherapy and chemotherapy, more targeted therapies and immunotherapies determined by tumour expression of molecular markers have been added to the treatment armamentarium [3]. Personalized biomarker-driven NSCLC therapy targeting epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR), anaplastic lymphoma kinase (ALK), and immunotherapy targeting the programmed death-ligand 1 (PD-L1) is now available [4].

The PD-1/PD-L1 checkpoint pathway has emerged as one of the key targets in NSCLC management, with immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) such as durvalumab, pembrolizumab, nivolumab, and atezolizumab significantly improving progression-free survival (PFS) and overall survival (OS) in PD-L1-positive patients [5][6][7][8][9][10]. Despite their success, accurate PD-L1 assessment remains challenging. Immunohistochemistry (IHC) is the current gold standard for PD-L1 quantification but suffers from several key limitations—it is invasive, prone to sampling errors, and fails to capture tumour heterogeneity, limiting its reliability as a predictive biomarker [11][12][13]. These challenges underscore the need for a non-invasive and comprehensive method for PD-L1 evaluation in NSCLC patients.

Given the limitations of IHC-based PD-L1 detection, there has been a growing interest in exploring radiomic features obtained from computed tomography (CT) and positron emission tomography/CT (PET/CT) with ^{18}F -fluorodeoxyglucose (^{18}F -FDG) imaging as a non-invasive alternative, extending its applications beyond traditional diagnostics [14]. Alongside conventional radiotracer uptake evaluation performed using Standardized Uptake Value (SUV) (a widely used PET imaging metric for assessing tumour metabolism), advanced computational approaches such as artificial intelligence and deep learning models enhance the extraction and interpretation of high dimensional features from PET-CT scans. By analysing the shape, intensity, and texture features of tumours, radiomics provides a non-invasive method to assess tumour biology and predict therapeutic outcomes [15][16][17].

Early radiomics models for PD-L1 prediction, despite demonstrating moderate performance (with accuracies around 68% and Area Under the Curves (AUCs) ranging from 0.706 to 0.84 [18][19]), face critical limitations. These models are predominantly based on small datasets, leading to overfitting and compromised generalizability which is a serious concern for clinical applications. Moreover, their focus on localized tumour regions neglects systemic metabolic activity, an important facet of tumour biology that could significantly enhance predictive accuracy. This oversight highlights a clear gap: the inability to fully capture the complex, systemic nature of tumour behaviour. Addressing this by integrating systemic metabolic information into deep-learning based radiomic analyses is essential for developing robust, clinically applicable PD-L1 prediction models.

Several studies have applied deep learning to PD-L1 assessment, demonstrating its potential to enhance accuracy and reproducibility. Deep learning-based IHC analysis has shown 96% accuracy in automated PD-L1 scoring from whole-slide histopathology images, matching

expert pathologist performance while reducing interobserver variability [20]. Additionally, weakly supervised deep learning models trained on PD-L1 IHC slides achieved AUCs of 0.88 in NSCLC cohorts, surpassing conventional manual scoring in predicting immunotherapy response [21]. Beyond histopathology, radiology-based deep learning models have been developed for non-invasive PD-L1 prediction, offering an alternative to biopsy-based assessments. A recent study trained a 3D residual CNN on FDG-PET/CT images from 697 NSCLC patients, achieving AUCs of ≥ 0.82 across internal and external cohorts, and showing prognostic value comparable to IHC-determined PD-L1 expression [22]. Similarly, a DenseNet-based CNN model analysing CT images combined with handcrafted radiomic features and clinical data achieved AUCs exceeding 0.90, reinforcing the importance of multimodal learning for PD-L1 prediction [23]. These studies indicate that deep learning can extract complex imaging patterns linked to PD-L1 expression, outperforming conventional radiomics approaches.

Furthermore, Fully Connected Neural Networks (FCNNs) have gained traction in oncology imaging due to their ability to capture high-dimensional patterns and learn hierarchical feature representations. A study on breast cancer Ki-67 classification integrated ultrasound radiomics with an FCNN, achieving high diagnostic accuracy and demonstrating clinical utility in biomarker-based cancer assessment [24]. A bibliometric analysis of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in breast cancer imaging further identified FCNNs as a key deep learning method for enhancing clinical decision-making [25]. Given these successes, applying FCNNs to whole-body PET/CT radiomics in NSCLC may enhance PD-L1 prediction by incorporating systemic metabolic activity into the analysis.

This study builds upon prior deep learning advancements by implementing an FCNN-based radiomics model to predict PD-L1 expression using whole-body and lung-segmented ^{18}F -FDG PET/CT scans. By analysing radiomic features at both the feature and patient levels, this approach seeks to capture systemic metabolic activity to overcome the limitations of localized tumour analysis, leverage deep learning's automated feature extraction to enhance PD-L1 prediction, and compare whole-body versus lung-segmented imaging to determine the most effective input for FCNN models. This study contributes to the growing field of AI-driven oncology diagnostics by demonstrating how deep learning can augment traditional radiomics to refine PD-L1 assessment, paving the way for non-invasive, data-driven approaches in immunotherapy decision-making.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Data Collection

The present research utilized imaging and tissue expression data collated for an institutionally-approved audit from 308 patients diagnosed with NSCLC who underwent ^{18}F -FDG PET/CT examinations at the Nuclear Medicine Department of Castle Hill Hospital between December 2019 and January 2023. Among these patients, 207 were classified as PD-L1-positive, while 101 were PD-L1-negative, based on IHC analyses. All imaging data were stored in Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) format and retrieved using Mirada DBx software. The scans consisted of fused PET/CT images with attenuation correction applied to

account for tissue photon attenuation and ensure quantitative accuracy. Each PET/CT scan contained over 300 axial slices, capturing cross-sectional representations of the body. For targeted analysis, slices numbered 120 to 260, corresponding to the thoracic region encompassing the lungs, were selected. These selections were validated through consultations with a radiologist and verified using the Mirada DBx viewer. To ensure compliance with ethical guidelines, all patient data was fully anonymized before analysis. The dataset exhibited an inherent class imbalance, with 67% of cases classified as PD-L1-positive and 33% as PD-L1-negative. To mitigate the impact of this imbalance and improve model generalizability, the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) was applied during pre-processing, ensuring that the dataset remained balanced for training and evaluation.

2.2. Data Preprocessing

DICOM images were processed using Python 3.8. Each axial slice was resized to 512×512 pixels through bilinear interpolation to standardize image dimensions. Pixel intensity values were scaled between 0 and 1 by normalizing with the maximum intensity value of each slice. A Gaussian filter with a sigma value of 1 was applied using the scikit-image library to smooth the images.

2.3. Lung Segmentation

Lung regions were segmented from the PET/CT scans by selecting axial slices spanning the thoracic region (slices 120-260). Otsu's thresholding method, implemented via OpenCV, was applied to each slice to generate binary masks delineating lung tissue from surrounding structures. The segmentation results were reviewed and validated by a radiologist to ensure accuracy.

2.4. Feature Extraction

Radiomic features were extracted using PyRadiomics, capturing various quantitative descriptors, including first-order statistics, texture, and shape-based metrics. Each slice was processed separately to reflect heterogeneity associated with PD-L1 expression.

Two datasets were generated:

1. Whole-body dataset: Radiomic features from the entire PET/CT scan.
2. Lung dataset: Features extracted solely from segmented lung regions (slices 120–260).

For analysis, two approaches were applied:

- Feature-level: Each slice's radiomic features were treated as independent data points.
- Patient-level: Features were aggregated by computing the mean across all slices per patient, creating a single feature vector per patient.

2.5. Feature Engineering

Feature engineering and selection were performed to optimize model performance. First, all extracted features were compiled into a DataFrame, with non-numeric values excluded and

missing data replaced with zeros. StandardScaler was then applied to normalize the feature set, ensuring uniformity across different scales. For the whole-body dataset at the feature level, Elastic Net regression with five-fold cross-validation was utilized to select the most relevant features. By incorporating both L1 and L2 regularization penalties, this approach helped mitigate overfitting, retaining only features with non-zero coefficients for model training. For the lung dataset and patient-level analysis, feature importance was assessed using a random forest classifier, as Elastic Net regression proved less effective in these contexts. Importance scores were calculated based on the Gini impurity criterion, and only features with a score above 0.01 were retained for further modelling.

2.6. Deep Learning Model Development, Training, and Evaluation

A FCNN was implemented to predict PD-L1 expression using radiomic features. The network architecture can be seen in Figure 1, and consisted of an input layer with neurons corresponding to the selected features, followed by two to three hidden layers with ReLU activation and dropout layers to reduce overfitting. The output layer contained a single neuron with sigmoid activation for binary classification. Model optimization was conducted in two iterations: the first (FCNN Model 2) involved increasing the number of hidden layers, reducing neurons per layer, and adjusting dropout rates, the optimizer, and batch size. The second iteration (FCNN Model 3) further refined dropout rates, neuron distribution, and learning rate adjustments. Hyperparameters were fine-tuned using RandomizedSearchCV, and the optimal configuration of the best-performing model is detailed in Table 1. The dataset was divided into training (80%) and testing (20%) subsets using stratified sampling to maintain class balance. Model performance was assessed using accuracy, ROC-AUC, and F1-score, while training and validation loss curves were examined to track convergence and detect potential overfitting.

Model	Strategy	Parameters Tuned	Details
FCNN	1st Hyperparameter Tuning (FCNN Model 2)	Hidden Layers, Dropout Rates, Optimizer, Epochs, Batch Size	Hidden_Layers=[64, 32, 16], Dropout_Rates=[0.2, 0.2, 0.1], Optimizer=sgd, Epochs=100, Batch_Size=16
	2nd Hyperparameter Tuning (FCNN Model 3)	Hidden Layers, Dropout Rates, Optimizer, Epochs, Batch Size	Hidden_Layers=[256, 128], Dropout_Rates=[0.2, 0.3], Optimizer=rmsprop, Epochs=50, Batch_Size=8

Table 1. Summary of the hyperparameters used with the different models tested.

Figure 1: Fully Connected Neural Network (FCNN) Base Architecture (FCNN Model 1) for Binary Classification of PD-L1 Expression in NSCLC Patients.

2.6.5. Software and Libraries

All analyses were performed in Python using libraries including Tensorflow for FCNN training, Scikit-learn for data processing and model evaluation, PyRadiomics for feature extraction and Matplotlib for visualization.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Lung Segmentation and Visualization

The visualization and analysis of whole-body ^{18}F -FDG PET/CT images using the Mirada DBx viewer identified slices numbered 120 to 260 as the most relevant for lung related analysis. These slices cover the thoracic region, where NSCLC tumours are typically located. Within this slice range, the lung anatomy and tumour sites were clearly visible, as demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Fused coronal view of a FDG-PET/CT image highlighting the tumour seen as an area of high uptake in the right upper lung region. The lung area is indicated by the arrow, showcasing the specific region where the tumour is located.

3.2. Feature Extraction, Selection and Preprocessing

A total of 98 radiomic features were extracted from PET scan data for both the whole-body and lung datasets. The whole-body dataset comprised 134,590 slices, while the lung dataset contained 43,142 slices. Aggregating features at the patient level resulted in a dataset of 307 patients. Feature selection reduced the number of features across datasets. In the whole-body dataset at the feature level, Elastic Net regression with five-fold cross-validation selected 27 features. For the lung dataset at feature-level and patient-level analyses (whole-body and lung), random forest feature importance identified 24 to 39 key features (Table 2).

Dataset	Level	Feature Selection Type	Features (Before Selection)	Features (After Selection)
Whole-body dataset	Feature Level	Elastic net	98	27
Whole-body dataset	Patient Level	Random forest	98	36
Lung dataset	Feature	Random forest	98	24

	Level			
Lung dataset	Patient Level	Random forest	98	39

Table 2. Feature selection summary for whole-body and lung dataset

An initial class imbalance was observed, with PD-L1-positive cases constituting 67% of the dataset and PD-L1-negative cases 33%. SMOTE application resulted in a balanced 50:50 distribution of PD-L1-positive and PD-L1-negative cases.

3.3. Model Performance (Feature-Level Analysis)

The best-performing model at feature-level, FCNN Model 2, optimized through the first hyperparameter tuning, achieved the highest accuracy and ROC-AUC scores (Table 3). The confusion matrix (Figure 3) further illustrates the model's predictive capability, with 8,926 true negatives, 17,725 true positives, 12 false positives and 255 false negatives. The model exhibited low misclassification rates with minimal false positives and false negatives, indicating strong discrimination ability in PD-L1 classification. Additionally, the stable training and validation convergence observed (Figure 4) suggests good generalization performance across the dataset .

Dataset	Model Configuration	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy	ROC-AUC
Whole-body dataset	Base Model (FCNN Model 1)	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.996
	1st Hyperparameter Tuning (FCNN Model 2)	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.997
	2nd Hyperparameter Tuning (FCNN Model 2)	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.994
Lung data	Base Model (FCNN Model 1)	0.69	0.57	0.55	0.71	0.695
	1st Hyperparameter Tuning (FCNN Model 2)	0.68	0.69	0.61	0.69	0.600
	2nd Hyperparameter Tuning (FCNN Model 2)	0.69	0.70	0.62	0.70	0.660

Table 3: Performance metrics for deep learning models (feature-level analysis). The best performing model (FCNN 2) is marked in bold.

Figure 3: Confusion matrix for the best performing FCNN Model (FCNN model 2) on whole-body dataset at a feature level, the model achieved the highest accuracy and ROC-AUC.

Figure 4: Training and validation loss curve for the FCNN Model 2 After first hyperparameter tuning at feature level.

3.4. Model Performance (Patient-Level)

The best-performing model at patient level was the FCNN Model 2 (first hyperparameter tuning), achieving high classification accuracy (98%), with an ROC-AUC of 0.990 for the whole-body dataset (Table 4). The confusion matrix (Figure 5) confirms strong classification performance, with a high true positive rate and minimal misclassifications. In contrast, models trained on lung data demonstrated significantly lower performance. The best lung dataset model (FCNN Model 2) achieved an accuracy of 71% and an ROC-AUC of 0.52, highlighting the inferior predictive power of localized imaging (Table 4). Additionally, training and validation loss curves (Figure 6) indicate that the FCNN model converged effectively, with minimal overfitting, suggesting good generalization ability.

Figure 5: Confusion matrix for the best performing FCNN model (FCNN model 2) on whole-body dataset at a patient level, the model achieved the highest accuracy and ROC-AUC.

Figure 6: Training and validation loss curve for the FCNN model 2 after first hyperparameter tuning at patient level.

Dataset	Model configuration	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy	ROC-AUC
Whole-body dataset	Base Model (FCNN Model 1)	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.995
	1st Hyperparameter Tuning (FCNN Model 2)	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.990
	2nd Hyperparameter Tuning (FCNN Model 3)	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.990
Lung Data	Base Model (FCNN Model 1)	0.63	0.68	0.64	0.68	0.42
	1st Hyperparameter Tuning (FCNN Model 2)	0.50	0.71	0.59	0.71	0.52
	2nd Hyperparameter Tuning (FCNN Model 2)	0.59	0.65	0.61	0.65	0.64

Table 4: Performance metrics for deep learning models (patient-level analysis). The best performing model (FCNN 2) is marked in bold

4.0 DISCUSSION

The emergence of PD-1/PD-L1 checkpoint inhibitors has revolutionized the treatment landscape for NSCLC, reinforcing the critical role of PD-L1 expression as a biomarker for predicting immunotherapy response. Accurate PD-L1 assessment is essential for guiding treatment decisions and optimizing patient outcomes [26][27]. However, conventional immunohistochemistry (IHC)-based PD-L1 evaluation remains invasive, prone to sampling bias, and limited in its ability to capture tumour heterogeneity. This study addresses these limitations by using radiomic features extracted from whole-body and lung PET/CT data to predict PD-L1 expression using both deep-learning based feature-level and patient-level analyses.

The results consistently demonstrated that models trained on whole-body PET/CT data outperformed those trained on lung-only data across multiple evaluation metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC (Tables 3 and 4). This finding aligns with previous research suggesting that systemic metabolic activity provides crucial prognostic information beyond localized tumour imaging [28][29]. Specifically, the FCNN model, chosen for its universal function approximation capability and ability to model complex nonlinear relationships, achieved superior predictive performance on radiomic datasets. By automatically capturing intricate feature interactions without the need for manual selection, the FCNN effectively leveraged the full predictive power of radiomic data [30][31][32]. Additionally, advancements in interpretability techniques such as saliency maps and layer-wise relevance propagation further enhance the explainability of FCNN-based predictions, making them a valuable tool for clinical decision support [33].

At the feature level, our FCNN model—after its first hyperparameter tuning (FCNN Model 2)—demonstrated exceptional performance on whole-body PET/CT data, achieving 99.1% accuracy and an ROC-AUC of 0.998. In contrast, when the same approach was applied to lung-segmented data, the performance dropped markedly, with accuracy declining to 71% and the ROC-AUC to 0.70 (Table 3). This disparity underscores the predictive value of systemic metabolic activity in PD-L1 assessment and suggests that limiting analysis to localized tumor regions may omit critical biomarker-related variations.

At the patient level, aggregation techniques such as mean feature aggregation improved model robustness and generalization. The tuned FCNN model trained on whole-body data achieved an impressive 98% accuracy and an ROC-AUC of 0.995, clearly outperforming previous studies that reported lower ROC-AUC values of 0.88 and 0.82 [21][22]. Conversely, models based solely on lung data demonstrated significantly poorer performance, with accuracy falling to 65% and the ROC-AUC decreasing to 0.64 (Table 4). These differences further emphasize the importance of incorporating systemic metabolic information for accurate PD-L1 prediction. A recent study focusing solely on lung-segmented PET/CT data reported an ROC-AUC of 0.82 for PD-L1 classification [35], which contrasts sharply with the 0.99 ROC-AUC achieved by our whole-body imaging approach. This clear disparity in predictive power demonstrates the enhanced benefits of integrating systemic metabolic information. Furthermore, while previous

deep learning studies based exclusively on tumor regions have reported ROC-AUC values ranging from 0.82 to 0.95 [36][37], our findings suggest that PD-L1 expression is influenced by broader metabolic activity beyond the tumor site. Together, these comparisons reinforce the need for a holistic radiomic assessment in NSCLC rather than relying solely on localized tumor imaging.

While this study demonstrates the predictive superiority of whole-body radiomics in PD-L1 assessment, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the dataset used in this study was derived from a single institution, which may limit the generalizability of findings across diverse populations. Future research should validate these results using multi-centre datasets with a larger sample size. Additionally, although the FCNN model achieved high predictive performance, external validation on independent cohorts is necessary to confirm its clinical applicability. Lastly, while this study focused on PD-L1 prediction, future work should explore the potential of whole-body radiomics for assessing additional biomarkers and treatment response across a broader range of cancers.

Overall, these findings confirm that incorporating whole-body metabolic data into radiomic analyses significantly enhances PD-L1 prediction accuracy, surpassing traditional localized imaging approaches. By leveraging deep learning for automated feature extraction and systemic metabolic integration, this study contributes to the advancement of AI-driven oncology diagnostics. If validated in larger, multi-institutional cohorts, this approach could transform biomarker-based decision-making in NSCLC, leading to more precise and personalized immunotherapy strategies.

5.0 CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that whole-body [18F]FDG PET/CT imaging, when analysed using deep learning models, significantly outperforms lung-only imaging in predicting PD-L1 expression in NSCLC patients. The superior performance of whole-body imaging models highlights the critical role of systemic metabolic activity in PD-L1 expression and immunotherapy response.

By outperforming prior studies that relied solely on localized tumor regions, this research reinforces the clinical value of a holistic imaging approach, which could improve patient stratification for immunotherapy. Incorporating whole-body radiomic analysis into routine clinical workflows may enhance personalized treatment strategies, leading to better therapeutic outcomes for NSCLC patients.

However, before this approach can be widely adopted in clinical practice, further validation with larger and more diverse patient cohorts is essential. Future research should integrate whole-body imaging with genomic and clinical data to enhance model accuracy and refine personalized treatment strategies. Such multi-modal strategies have the potential to revolutionize personalized oncology, improving treatment outcomes and guiding more effective immunotherapy decisions in NSCLC.

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